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Hybrid intelligence in 1·1·2 emergency call management: AI-powered interlinguistic and intercultural mediation / Inteligencia híbrida en la gestión de llamadas 1·1·2: mediación interlingüística e intercultural asistida por IA

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping multilingual 1·1·2 emergency communications. This paper illustrates the potential and challenges of AI-powered Interlinguistic and Intercultural Mediation solutions in Public Safety Answering Points (PSAPs) in Europe. Drawing on institutional reports, pilot projects, and scholarly literature, it offers a comparative analysis on how AI technologies such as Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), Speech-to-Text (STT), Translation of Speech-to-Text (TST), Speech-to-Speech Translation (STST), and Text-to-Speech (TTS) are being trialled to enhance accessibility and efficiency in 1·1·2 call centres. Results show that the adoption of these *Next Generation 112* (NG112) systems can accelerate triage, improve linguistic coverage, and reduce multilingual call-taker stress. However, risks of inaccuracy, hallucination, and demographic bias persist, requiring human oversight as reinforced by the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (OJEU, 2024). The study concludes that emergency-related telecommunications must rely on hybrid human-AI ecosystems, where technology supports the efficiency of the mediators and interpreters' tasks, particularly within frameworks such as the MILICITE (Alarcón-García, 2024), where empathy is preserved together with intercultural competence and ethical accountability.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Multilingual emergency call management; Interlinguistic and intercultural mediation; Public service interpreting

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Resumen: La inteligencia artificial (IA) está transformando progresivamente la comunicación multilingüe en emergencias 1·1·2. Este estudio muestra las posibilidades y los retos de la mediación interlingüística e intercultural asistida por IA en los puntos de respuesta a emergencias y seguridad (PSAPs) en Europa. A partir de informes institucionales, proyectos piloto y literatura académica, se ofrece un análisis comparativo de cómo herramientas de IA como el reconocimiento automático del habla (ASR), los convertidores de voz a texto (STT), la subtítulos simultánea en pantalla (TST), la interpretación bilateral automática (STST) y el lector de textos (TTS) se están poniendo a prueba para mejorar la accesibilidad y la eficiencia en los centros de atención de llamadas 1·1·2. Los resultados demuestran que la adopción de estos sistemas *Next Generation 112* (NG112) puede acelerar el triaje, ampliar la cobertura lingüística y reducir el estrés de los gestores de llamadas multilingües. No obstante, la falta de precisión, las alucinaciones y el sesgo demográfico pueden suponer un riesgo, lo que exige supervisión humana, tal y como recomienda el reglamento de IA de la UE (OJEU, 2024). Como conclusión, la gestión de llamadas de emergencia en idiomas requiere ecosistemas de inteligencia híbrida: humanos-IA, en los que la tecnología contribuya a una tarea eficiente de los mediadores e intérpretes, especialmente en el marco de los MILICITE (Alarcón-García, 2024), quienes aseguran la empatía, la competencia intercultural y la responsabilidad ética.

Palabras clave: Inteligencia artificial; Gestión de llamadas de emergencia multilingües; Mediación interlingüística e intercultural; Interpretación en los servicios públicos

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become one of the defining technologies of our era, permeating every sector of society, transforming areas as diverse as finance, healthcare, agriculture, education, mobility, and crisis management, and reshaping how we communicate, learn, and access services. Defined by the Spanish Government (2023) as a field of computer science that focuses on creating systems that are capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence, including learning, reasoning, and perception, AI draws upon diverse fields such as linguistics, logic, mathematics, psychology, and neuroscience. By processing vast amounts of data, AI systems are able to learn from experience, generate predictions, and optimise decision-making across increasingly complex domains.

These mechanisms have already become embedded in our daily lives across a wide range of domains. Personalised e-commerce, automated vehicles, precision agriculture, and the Internet of Things (IoT) devices are now routine. Examples include customer service through virtual assistants, used for product optimisation and sales planning; autonomous vehicles, some of which are equipped with the capacity to make a direct 1·1·2 emergency call in the event of an accident via Circuit-Switched (CS) eCall or Next Generation (NG) eCall technology; precision agriculture, with innovations such as irrigation systems, automated animal feeding, and brush-cutting robots and the IoT, which connects everyday physical objects such as household appliances or smart personal accessories, including clothing, watches, medical devices, or urban management systems to the Internet.

We can also find its applications in healthcare, finance, education, and security. In the health sector, AI supports diagnosis and treatment recommendations. In finance and insurance, algorithms optimise risk modelling and fraud detection. In education, AI underpins adaptive learning platforms, while in security, it assists surveillance, predictive policing, and border control (European Parliament, 2023; Telefónica, 2024). This versatility has made AI central to technological innovations, while simultaneously raising fundamental questions of ethics, trust, and professional displacement.

1.1 Multilingual challenges in Emergency Call Centres (ECR)

Within the realm of civil protection, AI is being deployed in Public Safety Answering Points (PSAPs), the nerve centres of emergency response. These operational hubs receive and process 1·1·2 calls in Europe and equivalent numbers worldwide: call-takers must rapidly assess, categorise, and dispatch resources while communicating effectively with callers often under extreme stress, where any delays or misunderstandings may carry life-or-death consequences. In such environments, some of the AI-driven solutions adopted are decision-support tools, dynamic call-taking protocols, and early pilots for real-time translation (Alarcón-García, 2025; EENA, 2024; Gizikis, 2024; Leety, 2024).

Among the most pressing challenges for PSAPs is multilingual call management, Europe's linguistic diversity, amplified by tourism, migration, refugees, and mobility, which means that millions of emergency calls are made each year by non-native speakers. The European legislation has long stressed that any person dialling 1·1·2 should be able to access help without language being a barrier (Council Decision 91/396/ECC; Directive 2002/22/EC; Directive (EU) 2018/1972). Yet speaking a different language is still a frequent problem not just for callers abroad, but for emergency-services staff regularly, and miscommunication can have a significant impact: "from slowing response times to influencing decision-making and, in some cases, compromising the safety of care" (ETS, 2025).

Operational evidence highlights the scale of the issue. Traditionally, PSAPs have relied on a mix of strategies to address this challenge: outsourcing to third-party interpreting services, forwarding calls to centres with appropriate linguistic coverage, recruiting multilingual call-takers, or even volunteer schemes (EENA, 2021). While these approaches extend accessibility, they also suffer from limitations. Third-party services involve extra costs, introduce delays, and raise privacy concerns (Cembrani, 2025). Forwarding calls adds logistical complexity and it cannot fully anticipate the breadth of linguistic demand (Vadana, 2025). Besides, multilingual recruitment alone does not seem a straightforward solution, given the highly specialised nature of call-taking tasks that require specific training and expertise (Alarcón-García, 2024). Nevertheless, the presence of foreign language speakers in a 1·1·2 PSAP ensures "accurate emergency response, reduces stress in emergency situations and supports international calls and cross-border incidents" (Vadana, 2025). All solutions considered, inclusive emergency communication requires systemic innovation rather than piecemeal fixes Leety (2024).

In the present circumstances, European emergency authorities are showing increasing interest in ensuring the provision of assistance in multiple languages. Emergency language services, as defined by Guo, Xiao and Guo, refer to "the provision of rapid language products, language technologies, or participation in language rescue operations for the prevention, monitoring, rapid response, and recovery of major natural disasters or public crisis events" (2024, p. 2). Thus, given the nature of the communications on this hotline, linguistic support should not be an optional add-on, but a foundational element of public service delivery, trust, accountability, and social justice.

1.2 Technological pilots in 1·1·2 emergency call management

This deep, structural change in (multilingual) emergency management has been initiated through technological pilots, which are beginning to complement human expertise. This involves testing cutting-edge *Next Generation 112* (NG112) architecture, which incorporates a "range of tools that facilitate digital communication with emergency services", for example, "video technology, location data, images, real-time text, and other digitally-communicated

data points” (Omda, 2023). These AI-powered tools enhance the efficient allocation of resources and the agility with which (multilingual) communications are managed.

AI-driven tools for the field of translation and interpreting in emergency call workflows involve: Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), Speech-to-Text (STT), Translation of Speech-to-Text (TST), Speech-to-Speech Translation (STST) and Text-to-Speech (TTS) software. Trials employing language transcription and translation such as LiveReader’s *ALTERNIS* and *NOTITIA AI* in Germany (Blaschke, 2025; EENA, 2024); Cestel’s *Natalía* in the Czech Republic and Spain; *Gladiá* in Italy, Sweden and Finland; and *Sharp Box* in Portugal and Sweden (EENA, 2024), together with initiatives such as *Omda Coordcom* in Valencia, Spain (Alarcón-García, 2025); *Carbyne* in the U.S. (Dizengof, 2024), AI Speech Lab in Singapore (NUS, 2023; Tan, 2018), and other AI models in India (Khan, 2025), illustrate how AI-powered solutions can enhance accessibility, shorten response time, streamline triage, and reduce operator stress.

For instance, the latest European Emergency Number Association (EENA) report (2024) provides preliminary findings on the *AI Special Project*. In Ludwigshafen, Germany, AI software (ASR, STT, TST and automatic summaries of the dialogues) “was used to translate 80 test calls and 600 emergency calls that were received in other languages, with positive results” (EENA, 2024, p. 12). One advantage was the system’s capacity to extract key data (e.g., address, symptoms, vital signs) and suggest entries for the call report, while the call-taker retained responsibility for confirmation (Blaschke, 2025).

At the same time, these innovations highlight the continuing need for human oversight and mediation, particularly in high-risk environments. In Trento, Italy, more than 2,600 foreign-language emergency calls were handled in 2024, with AI-based language recognition (ASR) reaching over 80% accuracy (Cembrani, 2025), but concluding that “the transcription technology was not sufficiently developed to work on emergency call audio” (EENA, 2024, p. 13). In Andalusia, Spain, “issues such as the lower quality of translation, the negative impacts of background noise, and the need for further training on emergency communication specific language” were highlighted (EENA, 2024, p. 11).

These data illustrate that multilingual accessibility is no longer an exception, but a structural reality of public safety, which implies that further improvements would be needed before this technology is ready for market.

1.3 Objectives of this study

This study, therefore, offers a comprehensive overview of the current state of AI-powered interlinguistic and intercultural mediation¹ (hereafter referred to as “mediation”) in emergency call management in Europe. It first outlines the theoretical framework of multilingual access to public services, then it describes the methodology used for the comparative document-based analysis. The results examine case studies and technological pilots to showcase both the potential benefits and the limitations of AI integration. The discussion reflects on the ethical, professional, and regulatory implications, before concluding with recommendations and future lines of research for building sustainable hybrid human–AI ecosystems in multilingual emergency communication.

¹ Although we primarily adopt this term following the line of research established by Raga Jimeno (2023), the designation *public service interpreting* is retained, particularly given its use in the sources consulted, which are closely related to PSAP operations, albeit with specific features that will be further addressed within the MILICITE framework.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Literature review

The theoretical foundation of this study lies at the intersection of Public Service Interpreting (PSI) studies, emergency communication, and translation and interpreting technology.

PSI has been defined as the communication between institutions and users who do not share a language, mediated by trained interpreters (Abril Martí, 2006). Rather than being neutral conduits, interpreters are co-participants who shape institutional interactions (Hale, 2007; Pöchhacker, 2012; Wadensjö, 1998). Therefore, PSI involves indeed much more than linguistic conversion; it entails navigating institutional structures, interpersonal dynamics, and culturally embedded systems of meaning. This is especially meaningful in contexts marked by urgency and high emotional stakes, such as 1·1·2 emergency calls related to public safety, health crises, natural disasters, or accidents.

In these communicative encounters, interpreters operate under conditions of high stress and limited time. And they function not only as linguistic conduits, but also, and mainly, as cultural and emotional bridges, facilitating communication between public service providers and individuals who may be vulnerable, traumatised, or linguistically marginalised. It is no coincidence that recent research has reframed interpreters in these settings as ethical gatekeepers who mediate not only language, but also rights, confidentiality, and cultural understanding (Parrilla Gómez & Postigo Pinazo, 2025).

Within the European Union, language diversity is both a reflection of its multicultural identity and a policy imperative. The EU's commitment to multilingualism is not just symbolic; it rather translates into tangible responsibilities for national and local authorities to ensure that emergency public services are accessible to speakers of all languages (OJEU, 1991; 2018). Thus, multilingual communication in emergency call settings becomes a critical point of entry for understanding the broader challenges and implications of PSI in today's societies.

A key sector where the intersection of language, urgency, and institutional response is especially acute can be found within the Public Services of Intervention and Assistance in Civil Protection Emergencies (SPIAEP, from its Spanish acronym) since they guarantee search and rescue operations, firefighting, medical deployment and law enforcement. Therefore, Emergency Call Reception Centres (ECRC, above-mentioned PSAPs), understood as civil protection units, operate under conditions that require rapid decision-making, clear communication, and immediate action, particularly when considering that for migrants and linguistically diverse individuals, the inability to express themselves effectively in the dominant language can become a critical barrier to receiving timely assistance.

2.2 The MILICITE framework

To better understand this reality, it is essential to introduce the MILICITE framework (Alarcón-García, 2024), which seems to be one of the most effective approaches to conceptualising multilingual provision in 1·1·2 emergency lines. Initially, MILICITE (from the Spanish acronym *mediación (mediador) interlingüística e intercultural a través de la interpretación telefónica en emergencias 1·1·2*) stands for Interlinguistic and Intercultural Mediation (Mediator) through 1·1·2 Emergency Telephone Interpreting. According to this paradigm, professional call-takers

trained in this type of mediation, telephone interpreting, and crisis management (Alarcón-García, 2025) should lead emergency response in multilingual settings.

Figure 1. The MILICITE Framework

By placing the MILICITE, as a professional activity, at the core of the ECRC, the model demonstrates that linguistic accessibility should be institutionalised rather than outsourced. In their role as call-takers, the MILICITE interview foreign citizens in their best language to ascertain the coordinates of each life-threatening situation (where, when, what, how). Throughout this telephone conversation, the essential information is recorded in the local language within the Emergency Communication System (ECS), in a structured and summarised manner, the register is upgraded employing specific terminology and the corresponding emergency protocol applied. Once this initial mediation stage is over (phase 1), the MILICITE must send the call report to the Emergency Response Teams (ERT) and remain available to facilitate a possible interaction (through telephone interpreting) between the callers and other SPIAEP (paramedics, security bodies or firefighters) before or while being deployed or at scene (phase 2).

The following diagram situates the MILICITE model within the overarching field of the SPIAEP; the 1·1·2 European emergency number is one of them. The three circles represent the core dimensions of mediation: interlinguistic (accurate transfer of meaning across languages), intercultural (awareness of cultural frames and references), and multimodal (integration of different communication modes, including spoken, written, and digital). Their intersection defines the MILICITE scheme as a holistic approach to multilingual emergency communication. Surrounding the framework are the interpreting techniques (bilateral interpreting; sight translation) and modalities (PSI and remote interpreting), following the distinction by the University of Vigo (Linkterpreting, n.d.), that are most relevant to 1·1·2 calls as these professional practices connect directly to the communication strategies needed in real-life emergency interactions. The red frame underscores that all these elements unfold within the specific institutional and communicative context of 1·1·2 emergency services, where time, accuracy, and clarity are critical to saving lives.

To better understand how the MILICITE framework materialises operationally in emergency settings, we will draw on the example of the *1·1·2 Comunitat Valenciana*, one of the Spanish regions with the highest levels of tourism and a substantial foreign-resident population. These professionals handled 24,753 foreign-language calls during 2025 in the Valencian region (Generalitat Valenciana, 2025), not merely mediating (phase 1) or interpreting (phase 2), but safeguarding confidentiality, ensuring cultural understanding, and providing emotional reassurance to distressed callers.

By embedding the MILICITE directly into the PSAP, the Valencian model avoids delays and reinforces trust, illustrating how PSI can be institutionalised in emergency contexts while at the same time it anticipates the hybrid skill set required in an AI-assisted future: digital literacy applied to crisis communication and mediation. This becomes particularly visible in the Valencian 1·1·2 Emergency Coordination Centre (ECC), which uses *Omda CoordCom*, an emergency call-handling platform that integrates dynamic question plans that adapt to caller responses and automatically rank incidents by priority, enabling faster dispatch (Omda, 2025) and triage support (Ferri, 2024).

That is, this algorithm-driven software functions as an emergency response system that structures call-taking through adaptive interviews, where the system tailors subsequent questions to the caller's input. This dynamic sequencing ensures that critical information (such as location, symptoms, or risks) is collected^o efficiently, even when callers provide incomplete or ambiguous details. In multilingual emergency calls, such structured support not only reduces the likelihood of errors and delays but also assists less-experienced call-takers in managing complex interactions with greater consistency.

2.3 AI-driven interpreting software: challenges and opportunities

With the arrival of NG112 architecture and its applications in emergency response, it is also possible to incorporate Computer-Assisted Interpreting (CAI) tools. Undoubtedly, the emergence of these “digital devices designed to support the interpreter in different steps of their work, from preparation to the very act of interpreting” (Fantinuoli and Montecchio, 2022, p. 2), has significantly expanded the technological landscape of interpreting. Moreover, AI-enhanced CAI tools offer multiple possibilities not only for professional interpreters, but also for trainees since they emerge as an “interesting solution to extract specialised terminology; for the review and quality control of interpretations; to write tests and materials that simulate real-life situations and to access tailor-made speeches with different accents” (Parrilla Gómez & Postigo Pinazo, 2025, p. 89).

These resources are currently reshaping multilingual communication in emergency settings, particularly those expanding the modalities of spoken and written communication. For instance, this is the case of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), “a technology that enables machines to recognise and transcribe human speech” and Text-to-Speech (TTS), “commonly known as speech synthesis, which involves the use of algorithms and software to generate spoken language from written text” (Parrilla Gómez & Postigo Pinazo, 2025, p. 89-90).

Within the 1·1·2 emergency call environment, ASR can assist in the rapid identification of the language spoken by the caller, thereby enabling the system to route the interaction more effectively by transferring the call to the MILICITE who works with that language combination. At the same time, TTS technology allows the delivery of pre-set messages in multiple languages, making it possible to communicate essential information about available services or unfolding emergency situations in a clear and standardised way.

Additional applications are also being tested to ensure a basic level of accessibility for callers who might otherwise face critical barriers to crisis communication. First, STT technologies allow oral messages to be converted into written transcripts in real time, thus supporting documentation and facilitating accessibility in PSAP environments. Second, STST operates as a form of bilateral interpreting, enabling direct oral interaction between callers and call-takers who do not share a common language by translating speech in both directions. Finally, TST transforms oral discourse into simultaneous subtitles, bridging accessibility gaps in contexts where audio transmission is compromised. Together, these solutions extend the functionality of AI in multilingual emergency interactions, not only by transcribing or synthesising speech, but also by enabling real-time interpreting and subtitling processes across languages.

Academic and industry reports reflect both enthusiasm and caution. Neural Machine Translation (NMT) and Large Language Models (LLMs) have achieved near-human quality in high-resource domains, yet perform inconsistently in specialised or low-resource contexts. For instance, one of these specific settings was studied by Briva-Iglesias (2021), who showed that legal translation remains error-prone due to terminological complexity. At the same time, Alfaify (2025) demonstrated that AI audiovisual translations in under-resourced environments, such as from Arabic and Hebrew into English, often produced misleading outputs in conflict-related contexts.

Recent studies provide further context by examining how these dynamics unfold within Emergency Medical Services (EMS) systems, which share key structural and communicative features with the 1·1·2 model. This alignment is precisely why EMS research is relevant here, as time-critical communication and operational constraints similarly shape the feasibility of AI-assisted solutions. In 2019, Turner et al. underscored that interpreters have long relied on technology in their workflows, but the integration of automated translation software in emergency response raises new questions about accuracy, latency, and professional agency.

On the one hand, Costa et al. (2023) studied how artificial-intelligence methods could transcribe and classify unstructured emergency-call audio within prehospital and EMS/ambulance services in Brazil. They used ASR and Natural Language Understanding (NLU) models to classify Portuguese emergency call data with moderate accuracy and concluded that “AI can be used to transcribe audio and extract and classify unstructured emergency call data in an emergency system [...] as an initial step towards developing a decision-making support tool” (p. 1).

At the same time, Luo et al. (2025) compared four ASR engines (Google Speech-to-Text Clinical Conversation, OpenAI Speech-to-Text, Amazon Transcribe Medical, and Azure Speech-to-Text engine) in noisy and dynamic medical settings (prehospital and EMS), finding variable performance across categories and “accuracy issues in time-critical and dynamic medical settings”. In parallel, Brandenberger et al. (2025) tested AI translation (Google Translate) in paediatric emergency consultations across five languages (Spanish, French, Urdu, Arabic, and Mandarin), showing adequacy in low-acuity cases but prone to persistent errors. They concluded that “its use necessitates careful monitoring, understanding of its limitations, and attention to dialect and literal translation risks along with equity considerations” (p. 1).

On the other hand, a growing body of research highlights that human judgement remains indispensable to detect errors, contextualise meaning, and prevent unintended consequences in AI-assisted interpreting workflows. Santos (2023), in press, documented the increasing adoption of these technologies in simultaneous interpreting, while noting its robotic tone and limitations, reinforcing the idea that professors Fantinuoli and Montecchio

(2022) had pinpointed some months before. They showed that latency in AI-enhanced tools directly affects interpreter performance, underlining the need for interpreters to actively manage when machine output can be trusted and when human correction is indispensable.

Following the same logic, studies of ASR, live STT, and Machine Translation (MT) tools in the European Parliament confirm persistent accuracy gaps if they are implemented with no human revision (Romero-Fresco and Fresno, 2023). Lungu (2024) characterised AI as “a transformative force for instant communication” but acknowledged that interpreters are increasingly repositioned as supervisors of AI output. These findings align with previous research emphasising interpreters’ evolving role as quality controllers, ensuring accuracy, empathy, and ethics in hybrid ecosystems. For example, Yin (2024) found that the introduction of AI-translated live captions has altered the visibility of interpreters, positioning them more as monitors of machine output than as sole producers of target language discourse. Similar conclusions are drawn in Tan, Orăsan, and Braun’s (2025) pilot study on the integration of ASR into remote healthcare interpreting, which demonstrated that while ASR transcripts can improve clarity and reduce certain errors, they also introduce new inaccuracies that require human oversight.

Finally, while these AI-driven applications, including NMT and LLM-based systems, as signalled by Bowker (2025a; 2025b), not only support linguistic diversity and transforming professional practice, but also provoke debates about ethics, sustainability, and environmental impact (posing challenges for social and climate justice), and the repositioning of human interpreters. Taken together, this research corpus indicates that AI integration does not replace professionals but reshapes their role toward supervision, correction, and quality assurance within increasingly hybrid communicative environments.

2.4 AI and the MILICITE framework

In multilingual emergency management, however, AI must be situated as a mere assistive tool. According to Jorge Suárez, Deputy Director of Emergencies of the Valencian Government in Spain, in high-pressure environments where seconds can mean the difference between life and death, relying on AI solutions or unsupported mediation strategies is neither efficient nor ethically acceptable (Alarcón-García, 2025). For multilingual emergency communication to be effective, it must be grounded in a professionally supported system that recognises mediation and interpreting as critical infrastructure.

Approaches like the MILICITE highlight the multilingual call-taker’s irreplaceable role as mediator and (bilateral) interpreter, which makes it necessary to use a critical lens for evaluating AI integration, pointing towards hybrid human–AI models. Recent technological pilots are beginning to complement such human expertise and, even though further work is needed before being ready for use by emergency services, they demonstrate how AI can support efficiency and inclusivity (Blaschke, 2025; EENA, 2024).

The *Alternis* project (LiveReader’s *Alternis* and *NOTITIA AI*) epitomises the state of the art. By using LLMs to process simultaneous audio, it offers automatic ASR and STT and uses Natural Language Understanding (NLU) to extract structured information such as addresses, symptoms, and vital signs. It can then suggest structured data fields for operators and perform synchronous STST across multiple languages (Blaschke, 2025). This software illustrates how AI can accelerate multilingual communication in emergencies, yet it also insists on *hybrid intelligence*: emergency operators confirm suggested data, supervise translations, and retain ultimate accountability, reinforcing the statement that LLMs should augment human decision-making rather than supplant it.

Regulatory frameworks also underline the necessity of human oversight and recognise that accountability and ethics cannot be automated in life-or-death contexts. On one side, the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (OJEU, 2024) classifies emergency-related AI systems as “high risk” subject to strict transparency, traceability, and oversight requirements. On the other side, in the United States, the Department of Health and Human Services specifies that automated translation may only be used under the supervision of a qualified human translator (DHHS, 2024).

Following this background, this study explores the future of language access to public services in the age of AI, with multilingual emergency call management as a case study (EENA, 2024). It analyses how AI tools can improve accessibility and efficiency; what risks they pose in terms of accuracy, bias, and ethics; what role 1·1·2 mediators-interpreters should retain as ethical gatekeepers, particularly under frameworks like MILICITE; and what implications arise for their training and professional identity.

3. Methodology

The study adopts a document-based comparative qualitative design, triangulating evidence from academic research, professional frameworks, and pilot projects, including operational case studies based on the adoption of NG112 technology, such as *Natalía*, *ALTERNIS*, *NOTITIA*, *Gladi*, and *Sharpi Box*, to offer insights into the potential of integrating AI-powered tools in PSAPs of some European countries. These technologies support real-time multilingual emergency management functions, including triage, transcription, translation, and dispatch.

To ensure methodological transparency, the selection of documents and case studies followed purposive criteria based on their relevance to multilingual emergency communication, the implementation of AI-driven tools in PSAP contexts, and their alignment with NG112 developments. Sources were selected to represent a combination of institutional, operational, academic, and technological perspectives, with particular emphasis on recent pilot projects and applied initiatives.

This research prioritises experimental measures, where institutional and operational sources provide baseline data, focusing on how AI in multilingual 1·1·2 emergency services have been conceptualised, operationalised, and regulated. In this context, the MILICITE framework provides an embedded model of professional mediation and interpreting to better understand the nature of this field (Alarcón-García, 2024).

The documents produced by the EENA articulate the strategic objective of eliminating language barriers in 1·1·2 and envision the development of multimodal emergency infrastructures through the AI project (EENA, 2012; 2021; Leety, 2024). They are complemented by operational reports from Germany, Trento, and Romania (Blaschke, 2025; Cembrani, 2025; Vadana, 2025, respectively), as well as news reports from Bengaluru and Singapore, which illustrate the global relevance of these developments (Khan, 2025; Tan, 2018). In total, 52 documents were analysed, including policy reports, academic publications, and technical and operational case studies, covering the period from 2018 to 2025, corresponding to the most recent phase of AI integration in emergency communication systems.

The analytical strategy unfolds in two stages. The first stage synthesises descriptive evidence of current multilingual management practices and AI pilot implementations. The second stage critically analyses these practices in relation to PSI frameworks and regulatory requirements, focusing on efficiency, inclusivity, and ethics. The rationale for selecting emergency call management as a case study lies in its dual role as a critical public service

and a laboratory for technological innovation. Emergency contexts demand rapid, accurate, and inclusive communication, making PSAPs an ideal setting to examine both the potential and limitations of AI in mediation.

Despite these efforts, the study presents certain limitations. First, the selection may not capture all ongoing initiatives, particularly those not publicly documented. Second, variability in the level of detail across sources may affect the comparability of findings. Finally, as a qualitative, document-based analysis, not all files include primary empirical data from practitioners, which may limit the generalisability of the conclusions. By triangulating institutional, technological, academic, and professional sources, this study aims to provide a robust foundation for assessing the future of interpreting in an AI-driven world.

4. Results and analysis

Given the document-based design of this study, findings are necessarily presented alongside their source material, as this approach ensures traceability and preserves the operational and institutional context in which the analysed practices are embedded.

The *EENA AI Special Project Final Report* (EENA, 2024) assessed the integration of AI into PSAPs, focusing on speech transcription and translation technologies tested across several European contexts. The pilots involved software such as Cestel's *NataliA*, LiveReader's *ALTERNIS* and *NOTITIA AI*, *Gladia*, and the hardware-based Augmented Hearing's *Sharpi Box*, deployed in Czechia, Spain, Germany, Italy, Sweden, Finland, and Portugal. Collectively, these initiatives confirmed the feasibility of embedding AI-driven transcription and translation tools within live emergency call workflows. In some cases, such as *ALTERNIS* and *Gladia*, the systems successfully processed thousands of multilingual calls, demonstrating that AI has the capacity to substantially reduce reliance on third-party interpreters and accelerate the handling of foreign-language incidents.

Nevertheless, the pilots also revealed persistent challenges. Accuracy frequently declined under noisy conditions, during overlapping speech, or when low-resource or minority languages were involved. In some cases, language detection software confused closely related languages, such as Spanish and Portuguese, which could create risks in high-pressure operational settings. Emergency call agents' feedback was generally positive, particularly regarding the capacity of these tools to support multilingual accessibility, but staff consistently underlined that human supervision remains indispensable in order to mitigate errors and address cultural nuance.

Beyond their use in real-time call management, several of the tested systems proved valuable for training, documentation, and post-call analysis, extending their usefulness beyond live operations. Hardware experimentation, particularly with the *Sharpi Box*, illustrated how portable devices can contribute to noise reduction and transcription support, though integration with existing PSAP infrastructure remains limited and contextual noise sometimes provided information that should not be filtered out. Across all pilots, the report emphasised the regulatory and ethical implications of deploying AI in life-critical contexts. In line with the provisions of the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (2024), these systems were classified as high-risk technologies, requiring transparency, data security, and human oversight at every stage of deployment.

Overall, the EENA report concluded that AI-based transcription and translation systems are already operationally viable in European PSAPs and can play an important role in strengthening multilingual emergency call management. However, their limitations preclude

full automation, making it necessary to embed them within hybrid human–AI ecosystems in which technology enhances efficiency and linguistic coverage while professional mediators and interpreters safeguard accuracy, empathy, and ethical accountability. Table 1 summarises the *EENA AI Special Project Final Report* (2024):

Software (Company)	Country / PSAP	Functionality	Results in PSAP
Natalía (Cestel)	Czechia – Fire Rescue Service of the Czech Republic; Spain – 112 Andalucía, SOS Deiak (Basque Country)	ASR, TST, STT and TTS.	Pros: Useful in tourist-heavy regions; supported call translation for reviews and call transcription (STT) for improving data collection during emergency communications. Good identifying names of specific diseases and medicines, and the names of roads. Cons: Accuracy issues with background noise and language-switching; limited in less widely spoken languages or when speaking quickly under stress; issues transcribing culture related terminology (e.g., names).
ALTERNIS (LiveReader GmbH)	Germany – Integrated Control Centre Ludwigshafen	ASR, TST, STT and TTS.	Pros: Successfully translated ~600 calls in other languages; staff highly satisfied. Cons: Language detection confused similar languages (e.g., Spanish/Portuguese); transcription delay of 1-2 seconds during calls; system not integrated into the PSAP management software used by staff; call-takers needed prior instructions.
NOTITIA (LiveReader GmbH)	Germany – Ludwigshafen	STT and co-pilot support tool: suggests questions, extracts data from calls	Pros: Strong support for hints. Cons: Beta tool; not tested on live calls; generative AI component immature, especially in medical knowledge.
Gladia (Websocket Technology)	Italy – Trento PSAP; Sweden – SOS Alarm; Finland – Rescue Department	STT and TST (99 languages)	Pros: Supported ~2,600 calls in Trento; effective language detection; readable transcriptions could be used as inputs for Large Language Model AI tools to provide summaries of emergency calls. Cons: Cloud-only created security issues (cannot be used offline); poor performance with noisy audio (screams), low network coverage, overlapping speech (noticeable delays when processing content, or in separating speakers during calls) and minority languages had less accurate results (the AI had been trained on English French and Spanish).
Sharpi Box (Augmented Hearing)	Sweden – SOS Alarm and Portugal (Lisbon and Porto) PSAPs	Hardware/software box for noise reduction.	Pros: Improved clarity in ~3.5% of calls; easy to use; good for noisy environments; reduce physical and mental strain on call-takers caused by background noises. Cons: The caller's voices could sound metallic; limited activation as background noise sometimes offered context (traffic, babies and children crying, sirens, and crowds).

Table 1. AI Pilots for Language Transcription and Translation in PSAPs

The findings revealed both the potential and the risks of integrating AI into multilingual emergency call management. With the analysis of institutional reports, pilot projects, and scholarly literature, four key domains can be highlighted: triage and prioritisation, multilingual accessibility, operator support, and ethical-professional implications.

4.1 Triage and prioritisation

One of the earliest applications of AI in PSAPs has been in triage. Omda's *CoordCom* uses dynamic interviews that adapt to caller responses, automatically suggesting priority levels for dispatch (EENA, 2024). This improves speed and consistency while reducing operator workload. Similar approaches are found in pilot projects integrating ASR with NLU to identify keywords and classify emergency type (Costa et al., 2023).

Evidence from medical contexts suggests that AI triage can be beneficial but uneven. Luo et al. (2025) compared four ASR engines in simulated emergency medicine settings, finding good accuracy in recognising some categories (such as mental state or allergies) but poor performance in others (such as medications and treatments). Such results underscore both the promise and the limits of ASR in supporting critical triage. Scholz et al. (2022) likewise showed that ASR improved stroke detection in Denmark by approximately 16%, illustrating the clinical value of speech-driven systems while also confirming the need for human oversight.

4.2 Multilingual accessibility

AI has been particularly relevant for improving multilingual accessibility. As EENA (2012) emphasised, nearly one in three travellers face language barriers when contacting 1·1·2. In Trento, AI-based language recognition already supports operators by identifying caller languages with over 80% accuracy (Cembrani, 2025). In Romania, PSAPs handled almost 32,000 foreign-language calls in 2024, reflecting the structural nature of multilingual demand (Vadana, 2025).

The *ALTERNIS* project illustrates the frontier of innovation as stated in section 2.4. Using LLMs and NLU, *ALTERNIS* processes caller and operator audio streams separately, extracts structured data, and performs synchronous STST across 42 base languages and more than 20 additional cloud-supported languages (Blaschke, 2025). This reduces reliance on third-party interpreters and shortens response times but still requires human confirmation of suggested data.

International experiences reinforce this direction. In Bengaluru, India, an AI-based voice assistant is being introduced on the 1·1·2 helpline, enabling communication in more than 15 languages for tourists, migrant workers, and expatriates (Khan, 2025). In Singapore, a mixed-lingual recognition engine is being developed to process English-Chinese code-switching and dialects, reducing transcription delays and ensuring inclusivity in a complex linguistic environment (Tan, 2018). Within Europe, the NG112 initiative promoted by EENA envisions next-generation emergency infrastructures capable of integrating voice, text, video, and geolocation data into a unified platform (Omda, 2023).

At the same time, risks remain. NMT performs well for high-resource languages but less effectively in low-resource or specialised domains (Briva-Iglesias, 2021). Alfaify (2025) showed that AI translations of audiovisual material often hallucinate, producing fluent but incorrect outputs. In emergency contexts, such errors could prove fatal.

4.3 Operator support and stress reduction

AI also contributes to reducing operator stress. Leety (2024) stated that inclusivity in emergencies must involve not only linguistic accessibility but also support for staff. Tools such as real-time transcription, noise cancellation, and automated summarisation can ease cognitive load, improve documentation, and provide training material for future operators. By filtering background noise and structuring call content, AI enhances both performance and resilience.

4.4 Ethical and professional implications

The integration of AI also raises questions about professional roles and ethics. The MILICITE framework in Valencia, Spain shows how interpreters can be embedded within PSAPs as mediators trained in intercultural communication and crisis management (Alarcón-García, 2024). While AI can handle routine tasks such as transcription or preliminary translation, it cannot replicate the empathy and cultural competence offered by human mediators.

Regulatory safeguards confirm this position. The EU AI Act (OJEU, 2024) designates emergency-related AI as high risk, requiring transparency and human oversight. Similarly, U.S. guidelines mandate that automated translation must be supervised by qualified interpreters (DHHS, 2024). These measures echo the scholarly consensus that interpreters serve as ethical gatekeepers (Parrilla Gómez & Postigo Pinazo, 2025), ensuring accuracy and justice in contexts where errors can cost lives.

In sum, the results present a double-edged reality: AI can accelerate triage, extend coverage, and support staff, but it also introduces risks of inaccuracy, bias, and ethical erosion. Hybrid models combining AI with professional mediation appear to offer the most sustainable path forward.

5. Discussion

The findings position AI as both an opportunity and a challenge for PSI. The evidence suggests that AI is most effective when used as an assistive technology. It can automate repetitive processes such as language detection, transcription, and data extraction, but cannot substitute the empathy, cultural awareness, and ethical reasoning of interpreters. As Alarcón-García (2024; 2025) argued in the MILICITE framework, mediators remain central to safeguarding trust and accessibility in emergencies. And, fortunately, the regulatory frameworks reinforce this approach: the EU AI Act (OJEU, 2024) and in the U.S., the HHS (2024) requires qualified human oversight for MT. These guidelines confirm that AI cannot be deployed as an autonomous replacement in life-critical contexts.

The accuracy concerns highlighted by Alfaify (2025), Briva-Iglesias (2021), and Luo et al. (2025) reveal the dangers of uncritical adoption. Hallucinations, omissions, or demographic biases (Zolnoori et al., 2024) could disproportionately affect minority or vulnerable communities, exacerbating inequalities rather than reducing them. While ASR has been shown to improve stroke detection (Scholz et al., 2022) and classification accuracy (Costa et al., 2023), these gains coexist with systemic weaknesses that necessitate human oversight.

From a professional perspective, interpreters face evolving roles. Industry analyses describe them increasingly as post-editors, supervisors or evaluators of AI output (Aneti and Asproset, 2024; Da Fieno Delucchi et al., 2025; Santos, 2023). Inevitably, this requires curricular innovation: interpreters must be trained not only in linguistic and intercultural

skills, but also in AI literacy, data ethics, and critical supervision. The MILICITE model anticipates this by embedding hybrid competencies (crisis communication, mediation and digital skills), but broader adoption is needed across PSI training programmes.

Ethically, interpreters remain irreplaceable. Translation studies have long shown that interpreters have an active role in dialogue interpreting (Hale, 2007; Pöchhacker, 2012; Wadensjö, 1998). AI adds a new layer of opacity, where algorithmic decisions on how to segment speech, prioritise terms, or render cultural references are hidden. Without human oversight, these processes risk reinforcing bias or producing unaccountable distortions. In emergencies, the interpreter's role as ethical gatekeeper is therefore amplified rather than diminished.

The discussion thus affirms the double-edged nature of AI. While Bengaluru and Singapore show how voice assistants and recognition engines can extend inclusivity, systemic risks persist. The most promising path is that of hybrid intelligence, where AI augments efficiency and human interpreters preserve ethics and empathy.

By situating multilingual call management within the broader field of PSI, this work argues that AI-powered solutions must be conceived as assistive technologies. Human interpreters remain indispensable for safeguarding empathy, cultural understanding, and ethical integrity, while AI offers opportunities to strengthen accessibility, inclusivity, and resilience.

6. Conclusion

This study has examined the potential and limitations of AI-powered interpreting solutions in multilingual emergency call management. The evidence suggests that AI can accelerate triage, support operators, and expand linguistic coverage, but that it also introduces risks of inaccuracy, bias, and ethical erosion. The overarching conclusion is that AI should be understood as an assistive tool, not a replacement for professional mediators (phase 1) and interpreters (phase 2).

The MILICITE framework demonstrates that embedding professional multilingual workforce within PSAPs remains the most effective model of accessibility. These language specialists combine linguistic, intercultural, and crisis-management skills, ensuring trust and empathy in high-stakes contexts (Alarcón-García, 2024). AI can strengthen such frameworks by automating routine processes, but it cannot substitute the human dimension as regulated by the EU AI Act (OJEU, 2024) and U.S. guidelines (DHHS, 2024). Emergency-related AI must remain under professional control, ensuring accountability and protecting citizens' rights.

AI has the potential to transform multilingual emergency services, but it cannot replace the professional mediator-interpreter who anchors trust, empathy, and justice. AI translations can appear fluent while concealing serious inaccuracies, a phenomenon known as hallucination and, in emergency contexts, such distortions could prove fatal. The future of interlinguistic and intercultural mediation in 1·1·2 emergencies lies in hybrid models where AI strengthens accessibility while humans safeguard meaning and rights. By embedding them within technological infrastructures, multilingual emergency communication can become both efficient and equitable.

Glossary

- ASR – Automatic Speech Recognition (Simultaneous language detection)
- CAI tools – Computer Assisted Interpreting tools
- ECC – Emergency Coordination Centre
- ECRC – Emergency Call Reception Centre (also PSAP)
- ECS – Emergency Communication System
- EENA – European Emergency Number Association
- EMS – Emergency Medical Services
- ERT – Emergency Response Teams
- IoT – Internet of Things
- LLM – Large Language Model
- MT – Machine Translation
- MILICITE – Interlinguistic and Intercultural Mediation (Mediator) through 1·1·2 Emergency Telephone Interpreting
- NLU – Natural Language Understanding
- NMT – Neural Machine Translation
- NG112 – Next Generation 112
- PSAP – Public Safety Answering Point
- PSI – Public Service Interpreting
- SPIAEPIC – Public Services of Intervention and Assistance in Civil Protection Emergencies
- STT – Speech-to-Text (Transcription)
- STST – Speech-to-Speech Translation (Bilateral interpreting)
- TST – Translation of Speech-to-Text (Simultaneous subtitling)
- TTS – Text-to-Speech (Convert text into spoken audio)

References

- Abril Martí, M. I. (2006). *La Interpretación en los servicios públicos: caracterización como género, contextualización y modelos de formación. Hacia unas bases para el diseño curricular*. [PhD Dissertation]. University of Granada.
- Alarcón-García, V. (2024). Ensuring accessibility and inclusion in the 1·1·2 emergency line. Mediation between life and death. *FITISPos International Journal*, 11(2), 23-39. <https://doi.org/10.37536/FITISPos-IJ.2024.11.2.366>

- Alarcón-García, V. (2025). *Interlinguistic and intercultural mediation in public service intervention and assistance in civil protection emergencies: The case study of the Emergency Telephone Service "1-1-2 Comunitat Valenciana"*. [PhD Dissertation]. University of Valencia (Spain).
- Alfaify, A. (2025). Examining the accuracy of human and ai audiovisual translation: A comparative. Analysis of Arabic and Hebrew in the context of conflict. *AWEJ for Translation and Literary Studies*, 9(3), 17-40. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awejtls/vol9no3.2>
- ANETI and ASPROSET. (2024). *Situación y perspectivas del mercado de los servicios lingüísticos y la comunicación multilingüe en España. Análisis Estratégico. Tomo I. Conclusiones. Proyecto de investigación art. 83 LOU nº. 516-2022*. Universidad Complutense Madrid. https://asproset.com/noticias/docs/2024_Estudio_de_mercado_Espa%C3%B1a_ES.pdf
- Blaschke, F. (9th of April 2025). *Synchronous translation in emergency calls by using AI*. EENA Conference and Exhibition 2025. Helsinki, Finland. <https://sl1nk.com/mvnxujb>
- Bowker, L. (2025a). Once more unto the breach. Investigating the effects of AI on translation practice, teaching, and research. *Digital Translation*, 12(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1075/dt.00013.bow>
- Bowker, L. (2025b). Multilingual scholarly publishing and Artificial Intelligence translation tools: Weighing social justice and climate justice. *The Journal of Electronic Publishing*, 28(2). <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.7100>
- Brandenberger, J., Stedman, I., Stancati, N., Sappleton, K., Kanathasan, S., Fayyaz, J., & Singh, D. (2025). Using artificial intelligence-based language interpretation in non-urgent paediatric emergency consultations: A clinical performance test and legal evaluation. *BMC Health Services Research*, 25(1), 138. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-025-12263-1>
- Briva-Iglesias, V. (2021). Traducción humana vs. traducción automática: análisis contrastivo e implicaciones para la aplicación de la traducción automática en traducción jurídica. *Mutatis Mutandis: Revista Latinoamericana De Traducción*, 14(2), 571–600. <https://doi.org/10.17533/udea.mut.v14n2a14>
- Cembrani, G. (9th of April 2025). Handling emergency calls in other languages. Operational challenges and opportunities. *EENA Conference and Exhibition 2025*, Helsinki, Finland. <https://l1nq.com/cz7jxg4>
- Costa, D. B., De Abreu Pinna, F. C., Joiner, A. P., Rice, B., De Souza, J. V. P., Gabella, J. L., Andrade, L., Vissoci, J. R. N., & Néto, J. C. (2023). AI-based approach for transcribing and classifying unstructured emergency call data: A methodological proposal. *PLoS Digital Health*, 2(12), e0000406. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000406>
- Da Fieno Delucchi, A., De Almeida, A., & Russo Dos Santos, J. (2025). How language industry jobs are “shifting left”. From translation to orchestration. *Multilingual. The New Language Industry Workforce. Remote, Resilient, and Redefined*, 235 (January), 33-39. <https://multilingual.com/magazine/january-2025/how-language-industry-jobs-are-shifting-left/>
- Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS). (2024). *Nondiscrimination in health programs and activities: Final rule*. *Federal Register*, 89(88), 37522–37773. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2024-05-06/pdf/2024-08711.pdf>

- Dizengof, A. (24th of April 2024). *5 ways AI is revolutionizing emergency response*. EENA Conference and Exhibition 2024. Valencia, Spain. <https://11nq.com/03b7n7i>
- EENA. European Emergency Number Association. (2012). *Multilingual Emergency Calls*. <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/multilingual-112-calls/>
- EENA. European Emergency Number Association. (2021). *Multilingual Emergency Communications*. <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/updated-document-multilingual-emergency-communications/>
- EENA. European Emergency Number Association. (2024). *AI Special Project. Final Report*. https://eena.org/wp-content/uploads/2024_12_02_EENA_AI_Project_Final_Report.pdf
- Emergency Services Times (ETS). (2025). *New research finds language barriers slowing response and compromising safety*. <https://emergencyservicetimes.com/2025/08/15/new-research-finds-language-barriers-slowing-response-and-compromising-safety/>
- European Parliament. (2023). *What is artificial intelligence and how is it used?* <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20200827STO85804/what-is-artificial-intelligence-and-how-is-it-used>
- Fantinuoli, C. and Montecchio, M. (2022). Defining maximum acceptable latency of AI-enhanced CAI tools. *TechLing2021. Computation and Language arXiv:2201.02792*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.02792>
- Ferri, P. (2024). *Deep continual multimodal multitask models for out-of-hospital emergency medical call incidents triage support in the presence of dataset shifts*. [PhD Dissertation]. Polytechnic University of Valencia (Spain).
- Generalitat Valenciana (2025). *Informe estadístico mensual "1·1·2 Comunitat Valenciana"*. [Monthly Statistical Report "1·1·2 Comunitat Valenciana"] <https://www.112cv.gva.es/documents/163565706/378522927/2025+-+Datos+estad%C3%ADsticos.pdf/d1b099f9-945b-47f8-bfe9-b0a4b2fcc5c0?t=1767339187806>
- Gizikis, A. (24th of April 2024). *What AI can bring to PSAPs and EENA's AI Special Project*. EENA Conference and Exhibition 2024. Valencia, Spain. <https://sl1nk.com/uafmpmw>
- Government of Spain. Prime Minister's Office. (2023). *Qué es la inteligencia artificial*. [What is artificial intelligence?] <https://planderecuperacion.gob.es/noticias/que-es-inteligencia-artificial-ia-prtr>
- Guo, X., Xiao, D., & Guo, Y. From crisis to opportunity: advancements in emergency language services. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 11, 1170 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03698-8>
- Hale, S. B. (2007). *Community Interpreting*. Palgrave.
- Khan, M.Z. (6th May 2025). AI voice assistant to aid 112 helpline in 15-plus languages in Bengaluru. *Business Standard*. https://www.business-standard.com/india-news/ai-voice-assistant-to-aid-112-helpline-in-15-plus-languages-in-bengaluru-125050601209_1.html
- Leety, A. (20th March 2024). How the Push for Inclusive Emergency Communications is Driving Technological Breakthroughs. *EENA blog*. <https://eena.org/blog/how-the-push-for-inclusive-emergency-communications-is-driving-technological-breakthroughs/>
- Linkterpreting. (n.d.). Universidad de Vigo. <https://linkterpreting.uvigo.es/>

- Luo, X., Zhou, L., Adelgais, K., & Zhang, Z. (2025). Assessing the effectiveness of automatic speech recognition technology in emergency medicine settings: A comparative study of four AI-powered engines. *Journal of Healthcare Informatics Research*, 9(3), 494–512. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41666-025-00193-w>
- Lungu, M. (26th January 2024). Innovating multilingual interaction: AI's influence on the translation and interpreting industry. *Polilingua*. <https://www.polilingua.com/blog/post/artificial-intelligence-translation.htm>
- National University of Singapore (NUS). College of Design and Engineering. (2023). *AI speech lab: Automatic speech recognition for public services*. National University of Singapore. <https://cde.nus.edu.sg/ece/project-4/>
- Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). (1991). 91/396/EEC: Council Decision of 29 July 1991 on the introduction of a single European emergency call number. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31991D0396>
- Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). (2002). Directive 2002/22/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 March 2002 on universal service and users' rights relating to electronic communications networks and services (Universal Service Directive). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0022&from=EN>
- Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). (2018). Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code (Recast). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX%3A32018L1972&from=EN>
- Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). (2024). Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1689>
- Omda. (11th July 2023). *What is NG112 technology?* Omda. <https://omda.com/what-is-ng112-technology/>
- Omda. (2025). *Omda Coordcom*. Omda. <https://omda.com/solutions/emergency/omda-coordcom/>
- Parrilla Gómez, L., and Postigo Pinazo, E. (2025). Artificial intelligence in the training of public service interpreters. *Language and Communication*, 103, 86-107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langcom.2025.04.002>
- Pöchhacker, F. (2012). Interpreting participation: Conceptual analysis and illustration of the interpreter's role in interaction. In C. Baraldi & L. Gavioli (Eds.), *Coordinating participation in dialogue interpreting* (pp. 45-69). John Benjamins.
- Raga Jimeno, F. (2023). Non-cooperative communicative situations and impartiality. Interlinguistic and intercultural mediation with asylum seekers. *Hikma*, 22(1), 63-94. 10.21071/hikma.v22i1.14517
- Romero-Fresco, P., and Fresno, N. (2023). The accuracy of automatic and human live captions in English. *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series – Themes in Translation Studies*, 22, 114-133. <https://doi.org/10.52034/lans-tts.v22i.774>

- Santos, E. (2023). How AI is gaining ground in simultaneous interpretation. *El País English*. <https://english.elpais.com/science-tech/2023-09-03/how-ai-is-gaining-ground-in-simultaneous-interpretation.html>
- Scholz, M. L., Collatz-Christensen, H., Blomberg, S. N. F., Boebel, S., Verhoeven, J., & Krafft, T. (2022). Artificial intelligence in emergency medical services dispatching: assessing the potential impact of an automatic speech recognition software on stroke detection taking the Capital Region of Denmark as case in point. *Scandinavian Journal of Trauma Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine*, 30(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13049-022-01020-6>
- Tan, A. (10th July 2018). Singapore to build speech recognition system to speed up emergency response. *ComputerWeekly.com*. <https://www.computerweekly.com/news/252444468/Singapore-to-build-speech-recognition-system-to-speed-up-emergency-response>
- Tan, S., Orăsan, C. and Braun, S. (2025). Integrating automatic speech recognition into remote healthcare interpreting: A pilot study of its impact on interpreting quality. *Proceedings of Translation and the Computer (TC46). Computation and Language arXiv:2502.03381*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.03381>
- Telefónica. (2023). *What are the applications of Artificial Intelligence?* Telefónica. <https://www.telefonica.com/en/communication-room/blog/applications-artificial-intelligence/>
- Turner, A. M., Choi, Y. K., Dew, K., Tsai, M.-T., Bosold, A. L., Wu, S., Smith, D., & Meischke, H. (2019). Evaluating the usefulness of translation technologies for emergency response communication: A scenario-based study. *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance*, 5(1), e11171. <https://doi.org/10.2196/11171>
- Vadana, A. (9th of April 2025). *Proficiency in a Foreign language: An essential competency for 112 call-takers in Romania*. EENA Conference and Exhibition 2025. Helsinki, Finland. <https://sl1nk.com/dzvcsv6>
- Wadensjö, C. (1998). *Interpreting as interaction*. Longman. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315842318>
- Yin, T. (2024). Has the use of AI-translated live captions in simultaneous interpreting changed the role of the interpreter? A study based on professional interpreters' perceptions. *The Translator*, 31(2), 214-231. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2024.2412923>
- Zolnoori, M., Vergez, S., Xu, Z., Esmaili, E., Zolnour, A., Briggs, K. A., Scroggins, J. K., Ebrahimabad, S. F. H., Noble, J. M., Topaz, M., Bakken, S., Bowles, K. H., Spens, I., Onorato, N., Sridharan, S., & McDonald, M. V. (2024). Decoding disparities: evaluating automatic speech recognition system performance in transcribing Black and White patient verbal communication with nurses in home healthcare. *JAMIA Open*, 7(4), ooae130. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/ooae130>